

Final Report

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Abstract

The effects of environment interactions include degradation of materials, thermal changes, contamination, excitation, spacecraft glow, charging, communication and navigation errors and dropouts, radiation damage and induced background interference. Sandia National Laboratory (SNL) is currently soliciting revolutionary ideas for GPS orbits that will result in dramatic improvements at the system level – radiation shielding performance, weight, cost, reliability, and operations.

This report makes an effort to evaluate the feasibility of new innovative radiation shielding composite materials being developed at the New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology, Socorro, NM. Many advanced technology systems demand materials with unusual combination of properties that cannot be achieved with the conventional metal alloys, ceramics and polymeric materials, especially the materials that are needed for space applications. In this study, an effort is made to understand the applicability of a layered composite (LC) developed at New Mexico Tech for deep space exploration.

These layered composites materials have potential for their radiation shielding applications in low orbit space. Further R&D is required for application in GPS orbits. The tasks include modeling the composites for effectiveness in high orbits and compare with established materials like Aluminum and Tantalum and propose candidate material composite

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Chapter 1

GPS ORBIT-RADIATION CHARACTERISTICS

1.0 Introduction

The effects of environment interactions include degradation of materials, thermal changes, contamination, excitation, spacecraft glow, charging, communication and navigation errors and dropouts, radiation damage and induced background interference.

It is difficult and costly to design systems that are completely free from radiation effects. Instead, a level of risk is assumed and minimized in the design phase and during operations. Unfortunately, current models of the radiation environment are not designed for risk analysis or space environment forecasting.

1.1 Orbits

There are essentially three types of Earth orbits: high Earth orbit, medium Earth orbit, and low Earth orbit. Many weather and some communications satellites tend to have a high Earth orbit, farthest away from the surface.

Figure 1 – Different orbits and altitudes [Image Credit: Wikimedia Commons/[Cmglee, Geo Swan](#)]

Satellites that orbit in a medium (mid) Earth orbit include navigation and specialty satellites, designed to monitor a particular region. Most scientific satellites, including NASA's Earth Observing System fleet, have a low Earth orbit. Figure 1 is a representation of the orbits found around the earth.

1.1.1. High Earth Orbit

When a satellite reaches exactly 42,164 kilometers from the center of the Earth (about 36,000 kilometers from Earth's surface), it enters a sort of "sweet spot" in which its orbit matches Earth's rotation. Because the satellite orbits at the same speed that the Earth is turning, the satellite seems to stay in place over a single longitude, though it may drift north to south. This special, high Earth orbit is called geosynchronous.

A satellite in a circular geosynchronous orbit directly over the equator (eccentricity and inclination at zero) will have a geostationary orbit that does not move at all relative to the ground. It is always directly over the same place on the Earth's surface.

1.1.2. Medium Earth Orbit

Closer to the Earth, satellites in a medium Earth orbit move more quickly. Two medium Earth orbits are notable: the semi-synchronous orbit and the Molniya orbit.

The semi-synchronous orbit is a near-circular orbit (low eccentricity) 26,560 kilometers from the center of the Earth (about 20,200 kilometers above the surface). A satellite at this height takes 12 hours to complete an orbit. As the satellite moves, the Earth rotates underneath it. In 24-hours, the satellite crosses over the same two spots on the equator every day. This orbit is consistent and highly predictable. It is the orbit used by the Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites.

1.1.3. Low Earth Orbit

Most scientific satellites and many weather satellites are in a nearly circular, low Earth orbit. The satellite's inclination depends on what the satellite was launched to monitor. The Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) satellite was launched to monitor rainfall in the tropics. Therefore, it has a relatively low inclination (35 degrees), staying near the equator.

Many of the satellites in NASA's Earth Observing System have a nearly polar orbit. In this highly inclined orbit, the satellite moves around the Earth from pole to pole, taking about 99 minutes to complete an orbit. During one half of the orbit, the satellite views the daytime side of the Earth. At the pole, satellite crosses over to the nighttime side of Earth [1].

1.2. Radiation in Orbit

The natural space radiation environment can be classified into two populations, 1) the transient particles which include protons and heavier ions of all of the elements of the periodic table, and 2) the trapped particles which include protons, electrons, and heavier ions. The transient radiation consists of galactic cosmic ray (GCR) particles and particles from solar events (coronal mass ejections and flares).

The solar eruptions periodically produce energetic protons, alpha particles, heavy ions, and electrons. Table 1 lists the orders of magnitude of the maximum energy of the radiation particles. The table shows that much of the environment is high energy, therefore, shielding is not effective for many types of radiation effects. All particles are isotropic and omnidirectional. **Table 1** shows the range of energy values for difference types of radiation in space.

Particle Type	Maximum Energy*
Trapped Electrons	10s of MeV
Trapped Protons & Heavier Ions	100s of MeV
Solar Protons	100s of MeV
Solar Heavy Ions	GeV
Galactic Cosmic Rays	TeV

* For engineering applications

Table 1 – Maximum Energies of particles [2]

1.3 Satellite Characteristics

Orbit information from the USA 128 GPS satellite is used to setup its trajectory around Earth in SPENVIS.

Satellite (COSPAR Designation)	:	USA 128
Mission Objective	:	Global Positioning Systems Satellite
Apogee	:	33,649 km (Above sea level)
Perigee	:	17,055 km (Above sea level)
Inclination	:	61.5° [5]

The USA 128, launched on September 12, 1996, is one of the 24 GPS satellites orbiting the Earth. These vehicles are placed in 6 orbit planes with four operational satellites in each plane [6]. It serves as the perfect example for simulating a GPS orbit trajectory to generate the radiation characteristics.

Figure 2 – Flowchart of radiation sources included in GPS orbit environment

The flowchart given in Figure 2 shows the different sources of radiation being considered, and the corresponding models used through SPENVIS to obtain the flux-energy plots.

1.4 Radiation Models

1.4.1. Trapped Radiation Flux

The most widely used trapped radiation models for engineering purposes are the AP-8 and AE-8 models for protons and electrons respectively. These are the latest editions of models produced by NASA. The models are further broken down into MAX and MIN versions for solar maximum and solar minimum respectively.

The population of charged particles stably trapped by the Earth's magnetic field consists mainly of protons with energies between 100 keV and several hundred MeV and electrons with energies between a few tens of keV and 10 MeV. There is also evidence for the existence of a narrow

region centered around altitudes of about one Earth radius containing trapped heavy ions which are believed to be decelerated anomalous cosmic ray ions; the intensities of these heavy ions are several orders of magnitude below the intensities of trapped energetic protons in this region [7].

1.4.1.1. Trapped Proton

The AP-8 model was used with Solar minimum conditions to simulate the Trapped Proton Spectra in the satellite orbit modelled in SPENVIS (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - [Invariant coordinate](#) map of the AP-8 MAX integral proton flux >10 MeV. The semi-circle represents the surface of the Earth, distances are expressed in Earth radii.

The energetic (above 10 MeV) trapped proton population is confined to altitudes below 20,000 km, while lower energy protons cover a wider region, with protons below 1 MeV reaching geosynchronous altitudes. The region of space covered by higher energy protons diminishes with increasing energies and the highest intensities are located inward.

Figure 4 – Trapped Proton Spectra

The differential flux decreases with increase in Trapped particle energy. **Figure 4** shows the Electron flux/day due to Trapped-Protons in the MEO orbit selected for the GPS data. Beyond the Energy level of 10Mev, the model exhibits 0 flux for further data points.

1.4.1.2. Trapped Electron Flux

The AE-8 model (Figure 5) was used with solar maximum conditions and confidence level of 50% (which is a probability based output, according to the Monte Carlo codes used in our simulation) to obtain Trapped Electron Spectra in the satellite orbit [8].

Figure 5 - Invariant coordinate map of the AE-8 MAX integral electron flux >1 MeV

The electron distribution is characterized by two zones of high intensities, below altitudes of one Earth radius and above two Earth radii in the magnetic equatorial plane, respectively, which are separated by a region of low intensities, called the slot region.

The location and extent of the inner and outer belts and of the slot region depends on electron energy, with higher energy electrons confined more to the inner belt, and lower energy electrons populating the outer belt to altitudes beyond geosynchronous orbit.

The general description of the radiation belts above represents what could be called the average particle distributions based on the static NASA models AP-8 and AE-8.

Importantly, the inner zone electron flux data are known to be contaminated from high-altitude nuclear-device detonations during the late 1950's and early 1960's [9].

However, it has long been established that the actual population is very dynamic over different time scales.

Figure 6 – Trapped Electron Spectra

Similar to the Trapped-proton spectra, **Figure 6** shows the flux distribution with respect to Electron particle energy. Flux values per day in the radiation environment is obtained, which decreases with increase in electron energy. Beyond 6.5MeV, the flux value drops to 0.

1.4.2. Galactic Cosmic Rays

Galactic cosmic rays (GCR) are high-energy charged particles that enter the solar system from the outside, the flux of which becomes modulated in anti-correlation with solar activity due to the solar wind. They are composed of protons, electrons, and fully ionized nuclei. There is a continuous and isotropic flux of GCR ions. Although the flux is low, GCRs include energetic heavy ions which can deposit significant amounts of energy in sensitive volumes and so cause problems to spacecraft's' electronics and humans in space. As for solar particles, the Earth's magnetic field provides a varying degree of geomagnetic shielding of near Earth locations from these particles.

The Galactic Cosmic Ray Spectra (Figure 7) was obtained for ions ranging from H to U ($Z = 1$ to 92), using the ISO-15390 standard model for the solar minimum condition.

The GCR ISO model is based on the semi-empirical GCR models of the Moscow State University (MSU). All formulas and parameters needed to reconstruct the models are included in the International Standard ISO Draft 15390. To account for solar-cycle variations in the GCR intensities, 12 month averages of the Wolf (sunspot) number are used. The variations of the large-scale heliospheric magnetic field are assumed to be proportional to the variations of the

Sun's polar magnetic field whose intensity and polarity are taken to be dependent on solar activity and on whether a given solar cycle is even or odd. The time lag of GCR flux variations relative to solar activity variations is taken to depend on magnetic rigidity of particles, on whether a solar cycle is odd or even, and on solar cycle phase [8].

Figure 7 – GCR spectra for H ion

Similar Spectra plots are available for the rest of the ions ranging upto $Z=92$, all of which will be included during simulation of shielding materials. The general trend of the graph is a lowered differential flux as the atomic number of the ion increases.

1.4.3. Long-Term Solar Particle Flux

An important consideration for spacecraft designers is the worst-case solar particle event that occurs during a mission. All naturally occurring chemical elements ranging from protons to uranium are present in solar particle events. They can cause permanent damage such as TID and DD which is due mainly to the protons. The heavy ion content is a small percentage of the flux but nonetheless cannot be ignored. Heavy ions, as well as protons and alpha particles in solar particle events, can cause both transient and permanent SEE [8].

Using the ESP-PSYCHIC model, the long term solar particle fluences were obtained for ions ranging from H to U ($Z = 1 - 92$), for a prediction period of 11 years to incorporate the solar event cycle into the radiation spectrum.

1.4.3.1. Worst Case Event

Knowing the initial distribution of solar proton event fluences, the worst case event can be determined as a function of confidence level and mission duration. The worst case event sub-function of the ESP-PSYCHIC is used to generate the radiation characteristics (**Figure 8**) during highest exposure within the prediction period.

Figure 8 – Solar Protons Fluence (ESP-PSYCHIC Model – Worst Case Event)

It should be noted that for **Single Event Upset** simulations, this model is not used. In such cases, the Short-Term Flux module is used, which corresponds to different models for its simulation.

Figure 9 – Solar ions Fluence for He (ESP-PSYCHIC Model – Worst Case Event)

Similar flux plots are generated for ions (**Figure 9**) ranging up to $Z=92$, which are included during material shielding simulations. As commonly seen, the flux decreases with increase in particle energy.

1.4.3.2. Total Fluence

During a space mission the solar particle event fluence that accumulates during the solar maximum time period is often the dominant contribution to the total fluence. The ESP-PSYCHIC (Total Fluence) is used to generate data radiation flux (**Figures 10 & 11**) throughout the prediction period.

Radiation shielding materials can be designed with Total Fluence data in consideration, as it is higher than data obtained from the Worst Case Event.

Figure 10 – Solar Protons Fluence (ESP-PSYCHIC Model – Total Fluence)

Figure 11 – Solar ions Fluence (ESP-PSYCHIC Model – Total Fluence)

Comparing the flux values of Total fluence and Worst Case models, it can be observed that there is a general trend for the Total fluence model to generate higher values of flux (As in includes the worst case scenario), and as such, the shielding material should be simulated in accordance with the Total Fluence model.

1.4.4 Short-Term Solar Particle Flux (only for SEU)

Single event effects are due to ionization when a single charged particle passes through a sensitive junction of an electronic device. They are caused by galactic cosmic ray and solar heavier ions, but for some devices, trapped and solar protons can induce SEEs.

SEEs can be induced by direct ionization by protons, but in most instances, proton induced effects are the result of secondary particles that are produced when the proton collides with a nucleus of the material in the device. Some SEEs are non-destructive, as in the case of single event upsets (SEUs), single event transients (SETs), multiple bit errors (MBEs), single event hard errors (SHEs), single event transients (SETs), etc. SEEs can also be destructive as in the case of single event latchups (SELS), single event gate ruptures (SEGRs), and single event burnouts (SEBs). Figure 6 shows a plot of single event upsets on the SEASTAR flight data recorders.

The upsets that occur in the poles are caused by transient particles. Because the recorder is also susceptible to proton-induced effects, the proton region of the SAA is clearly mapped out by the SEU occurrences.

The preferred method for dealing with destructive failures is to use SEE-hard parts. When SEE-hard parts are not available, latchup protection circuitry is sometimes used in conjunction with

failure mode analysis. For non-destructive SEEs, mitigation takes the form of error-detection and correction codes (EDACs), filtering circuitry, etc.

SEUs affect mainly digital devices e.g. microprocessor, memories etc. Most neutrons pass through silicon, however, the high LET (Linear Energy Transfer) particles lose their energy along a short path, heavily ionizing the silicon material. CMOS devices can also be affected by this phenomenon.

Single Event Transient effects are in the form of voltage or current spurious pulses caused by the charge collected through the ionizing event. The generated transient can propagate through the digital or analogue circuit and bring about the disturbance in the output signal. These can be difficult to diagnose since they are detected in other systems path or module than the generated event. As the operational frequency of current devices and circuits is continuously going up, the probability that SET will be triggered is increased.

Both ionizing and displacement damage affects different electronic components including bipolar and MOS-based devices. Moreover, the effects can also affect passive elements such as resistors and capacitors. The devices suffer mainly because of the ionizing effect. The influence of radiation strongly depends on the fabrication technology, characterized by the feature size, which is getting smaller.

Old technologies with the feature size larger than $0.35\mu\text{m}$ suffer mainly because of ionizing effects, yet displacement damage effects are negligible. The devices are able to operate up to hundreds of Gy of total dose within an acceptable increase of power consumption. Digital devices are sensitive to SEE, especially SEU and SEL. When dimension of MOS transistors get smaller, the devices are more susceptible to SEU as a result of decreased supply voltage and critical charge. Probability of SET effects increase with the operational frequency of electronic devices. However, modern CMOS technologies generally seem to be more resistant to ionizing radiation due to very thin oxide. Accumulated charges in the gate-oxide can be removed by tunneling.

The CREME96 solar fluxes model are based on averaged fluxes observed during the 19-27 October 1989 episode. There are three cases which are included within the code:

- Worst week: flux averaged over 180 hrs beginning at 1300 UT on 19 October 1989
- Worst day: flux averaged over 18 hrs beginning at 1300 UT on 20 October 1989
- Worst 5 min: peak flux averaged over 5 min observed in October 1989

Out of these, it is found that the “worst 5 min” case offers the highest flux values for the given energy levels for both protons and ions. Design of shielding should therefore, be in accordance with these values for the most effective shielding characteristics at all operating conditions.

1.4.5 Solar Protons

The plot shown in Figure 12 shows Flux for Protons with respect to Energy in MeV. We should note that these models are used only in case of Single Event Upset simulations and for Long-Term dosage calculations, the corresponding model (ESP-PSYCHIC) is used.

Figure 12 – Solar protons Fluence (CREME-96 Model – Peak 5 min) Solar ions

1.4.6. Solar ions

The plot in Figure 13 shows a similar plot of Differential and Integral Flux for **He** ion. Similarly, plots for all ions ranging up to Uranium ($Z=92$) is available and simulated within the code, which will be accounted for, during simulation.

Figure 13 – Solar ions Fluence (CREME-96 Model – Peak 5 min)

Solar proton and ions fluence were compared for the 3 cases included within the CRÈME-96 model, and it is observed that the Peak 5 min case offers the highest flux values, as the other 2 models create an averaged plot of the flux during the time period. Therefore, simulations should be based on the Peak 5 min model.

1.5. Case Study: Radiation Tolerance of a remote controlled, manipulator equipped vehicle [10]

Investigations have been carried out in order to assess and to improve the radiation tolerance of a remote controlled, manipulator-equipped vehicle. Operating in radiative environments, these robots have to withstand total dose stresses up to several 10 kGy. The complexity of tasks these vehicles have to perform makes it necessary to supply them with extensive electronic systems on board. Thus, it has to be taken into account, that semiconductor electronic devices are highly sensitive to ionizing radiation. The experiment was carried out by deploying a Co60 source producing a dose rate at the vehicle's location of 100 Gyh.

The test results gave evidence to the severe radiation sensitivity of the controller subsystems. None of them did withstand more than 400Gy. This can be explained by the large amount of highly integrated CMOS devices used within these components. CMOS devices belong to the most radiation sensitive semiconductor technologies.

In contrast to the controllers, which all failed at almost the same low dose level, the radiation response of the power electronic subsystems was quite different: they failed in a wide range of dose levels between 34 Gy and 1500 Gy.

The control systems should be shielded, whereas the power systems should be modified in order to make them more tolerant against radiation.

Power electronics has a comparable low complexity. That makes it possible to use TTL logic in order to establish the logic functions necessary within these subsystems. TTL is one of the most radiation hard technologies. Most of the power semiconductor devices that are used in these components are available as radiation-hardened types and can be easily exchanged against the built-in commercial ones. Furthermore, a lot of the used power subsystems are already sufficient radiation tolerant, as the irradiation experiment shows.

Any CMOS glue logic was replaced by TTZ logic. Circuitry modifications were performed as necessary. The MOS field effect transistors were exchanged by compatible radiation-hardened types available on the market. The outcome of the evaluation of the remaining electronic parts showed is an iterative process. This is due to the fact, that every step towards an increased irradiation hardness uncovers additional weak points of the circuitry design from an irradiation point of view. This strategy resulted in an evident improvement of the radiation tolerance. The mean failure dose of the investigated 15N regulators could be increased from initially 245 Gy to 1300 Gy after the first and then to 5500 Gy after the second iteration [10].

This case study could be used as a reference for radiation testing to be conducting on the candidate materials in currently proposed design. Depending on the electrical instruments which needs to be shielded, the type of shielding and materials used should be selected accordingly.

Chapter 2

RADIATION DAMAGE TO ON-BOARD SENSITIVE ELECTRONIC DEVICES

2.0 Radiation Effects

Energetic radiation can penetrate analog and digital components, causing temporary faults or permanent failures. The effects of radiation on electronic devices can be classified into following three categories:

- Displacement damage
- Total ionizing dose and
- Single-event effects.

Radiation effects that are important to consider for instrument and spacecraft design fall roughly into four categories: degradation from total ionizing dose (TID), degradation from non-ionizing energy loss (NIEL), single event effects (SEEs), and spacecraft charging/ discharging. Each effect requires a different environment definition depending on the physics of the effect and the interaction model used to predict the rate of occurrence.

2.1 Non-Ionizing Energy Loss

Damage from non-ionizing energy loss (also known as displacement damage) is cumulative non-ionizing damage in optical materials caused by solar and trapped protons and trapped electrons. Secondary neutrons that are produced in shielding materials or the atmosphere or neutrons from external sources can also cause displacement damage. The particles produce defects that result in charge transfer degradation. It affects the performance of optocouplers (often a component in power devices), solar cells, CCDs, and linear bipolar devices. Shielding has limited effectiveness against the damage. Cover glasses over solar cells reduce damage by absorbing the low energy particles, but they cannot absorb the high-energy protons. Shielding is not usually effective for optoelectronic components because the high-energy protons penetrate most realistic spacecraft electronic enclosures. CCDs are heavily shielded, however, secondary particle production can become problematic. Displacement damage effects are calculated from total particle fluence levels.

2.2 Spacecraft Charging

Differentials in electron environments can contribute to spacecraft surface charging and discharging problems. Sudden storms in the MEO and GEO orbit electrons produce “hot plasmas” that are responsible for spacecraft surface charging. Also, increases occur in higher energy electrons during storms. These penetrate to dielectric surfaces inside the spacecraft and build up to levels that cause discharges. Spacecraft in GEO and geostationary transfer orbits (GTO) are

particularly vulnerable to these effects. Electron fluence levels in MEO are also high enough to cause charging problems. Electron accumulation profiles for a mission must be estimated and analyzed for possible surface and deep dielectric charging effects. A useful tool for evaluating charging environments is the NASCAP 2K model [2].

2.3 Total Ionizing Dose

Total ionizing dose (TID) is cumulative long term damage caused by solar and trapped protons and trapped electrons. In microelectronics, TID causes threshold shifts, leakage current, and timing skews. The effect first appears as parametric degradation of the device and can ultimately result in functional failure. When a manufacturer advertises a part as “radhard”, he is almost always referring to its TID characteristics. Rad-hard does not usually imply that the part is hard to non-ionizing dose or SEEs.

It is possible to reduce TID with shielding material that absorbs most electrons and lower energy protons. As shielding is increased, shielding effectiveness decreases because of the difficulty in slowing down the higher energy protons. TID levels are calculated from the solar and trapped particles incident on the spacecraft.

In cases where parts cannot meet the top-level design requirement and a “harder” part cannot be substituted, it is beneficial to employ more accurate methods of determining the dose exposure to qualify the parts. One such method is solid angle sectoring/3- dimensional ray tracing. An accurate computer model of the electronics box and/or spacecraft is produced and average path lengths through sectors are calculated. With that information, total doses can be obtained for any location. The value of dose mitigation measures can be accurately evaluated by changing the model and recalculating the total dose. Doses obtained by sectoring methods must be verified for 5-10% of the sensitive locations with full Monte Carlo simulations of particle trajectories through the structure for many histories.

The radiation characteristics for a GPS orbit are simulated using SPENVIS. Different Models for Trapped Proton flux, Trapped Electron Flux, Galactic Cosmic rays and Long Term Solar Particle Flux are used to generate Integral and Differential Fluence with respect to Particle energy for each of the radiation source.

Chapter 3

RADIATION MITIGATION

3.0 Radiation Mitigation

Radiation resistance of electronic circuits strongly depends on materials used to manufacture the device. Silicon-based devices are relatively cost-effective and therefore widely used. For that reason the following information is devoted to silicon components, although some techniques can be adopted for different materials too. **Table 2** gives examples of electric components classified according to their radiation tolerance.

Radiation tolerance	Groups of materials
High	Metals, ceramics and inert gases
Fair	Bipolar ICs, rectifying diodes, hardened MOS circuits
Poor	Commercial MOS circuits, analogue devices, solar cells, power transistors and CCD

Table 2 – Radiation tolerance of materials and components

One can distinguish 3 main groups of radiation mitigation techniques:

1. Methods implemented during the design and fabrication process
2. Shielding of the most critical subsystems or components
3. Techniques applied to design rad-tolerant circuits or systems.

Only modification of the electronic devices fabrication process or shielding can allow protecting devices against Total ionizing dose (TID) effect and displacement damage.

The last group allows to immunize devices or systems against SEE, especially SEU and SEL. Hardening during design stage gives extensive freedom and therefore allows to design rad-hard devices that are able to tolerate errors provoked by neutrons and gamma radiation.

There are 3 levels on which the devices can be designed:

1. Modification of crucial technology parameters
2. Application of additional layout processing
3. Modification of electrical construction

3.1 Shielding

Neutron and gamma radiation shielding usually requires using of heavy and large shielding blocks, therefore they can be applied only when there is enough room. However, shielding is occasionally

more suitable from the economic point of view. The type of shielding material depends on final desired attenuated radiation levels, resistance to radiation damage, required thickness and weight, uniformity of shielding capacity, permanence of shielding and availability. For that reason, lead and concrete are the most commonly used.

Appropriate ordering of high-Z and low-Z materials can give factor-of-three improvements, while inappropriate ordering can negate any advantage. Accumulation of trapped charge in insulators can provide a total dose problem but this is very design dependent. It has recently been shown that the mechanical properties of polysilicon, itself, are not affected by even high (10Mrad) doses of cobalt-60.

Radiation causes the formation of color centers in optical materials as well as changes in refractive index and mechanical properties. Because there is considerable annealing in the low dose rate space environment and doses are limited for shielded components the parameter changes (loss in transmission, change in refractive index and dimensions) are generally small and vary linearly with dose [3].

More recently, a new Geant4 physics list has been created dedicated for space applications, radiation biology and radiation protection. It includes combinations of BIC, BIC-Ion, BERT, CHIPS, QGSP and FTFP models and has higher precision than the others for many hadron-ion and ion-ion interactions in a wide energy range. Based on the user's selection for the incident particle, SPENVIS automatically selects the appropriate physics scenario. For pure EM interactions (e.g. incident gamma or electron) the Geant4 Option 3 (emstandard_opt3) is used. This standard EM physics list is optimized for medical and space applications. Otherwise, the physics list QBBC is used to simulate additional hadronic interactions.

3.1.1 Gamma Ray and Neutron

Ionizing particles can produce photocurrent in active regions of devices and provoke upsets, called single event effects (SEEs). The influence of neutrons and gamma radiation on electronic components with the emphasized interactions are depicted in Table 3.

Radiation type	Energy range	Main type of interaction	Primary effects in Si and SiO ₂	Secondary effects in Si and SiO ₂
Photons	Low energy	Photoelectric effect	Ionizing phenomena	Displacement damage
	Medium energy	Compton effect		
	High energy	Pair production		
Neutrons	Low energy	Capture and nuclear reaction	Displacement damage	Ionizing phenomena
	High energy	Elastic scattering		

Table 3 – Neutron and gamma radiation effects on Silicon devices [4]

The post-design irradiation hardening of such electronic components High energy incident particles can interact with matter mainly in 3 different ways:

1. Ionization of the latter through interactions with shell electrons
2. Displacement of atoms nucleus, assuming that the incident particle has enough energy.
3. Nuclear reaction with the target nucleus

Neutron particles are mainly responsible for displacement damage. Therefore, when a high-energy particle interacts with matter, some of its energy is consumed by the ionizing process and the other part by the displacement damage.

Both gamma and neutron interactions are included within the models used for shielding analysis.

3.1.2. Damage due to Gamma ray

Gamma ray photons deposit energy in the components mainly by ionization. The portion of energy absorbed by the circuit during the whole exposure is determined as a total ionizing dose (TID). The ionizing effect can be caused by different kinds of ionizing radiation. E.g. Gamma, X-ray, UV or indirectly through secondary recoil particles. The principle ionizing-based damage effects in a bulk material are: enhancement of conductivity through production of excess charge carriers, trapped charge, electric and magnetic fields, and chemical effects. Photon interact with matter, depending on their energy, in the 3 different ways:

1. Photoelectric effect
2. Compton effect
3. Electron-positron pairs production

The damage brought about the ionizing radiation is primarily due to the trapping of the charge in SiO₂ and secondarily because of anomalies in the Si/SiO₂ interface. Incident gamma radiation produced electron-hole pairs in the insulator. For e.g. in SiO₂:

The amount of charge generated in silica strongly depends on the electric field across the oxide during exposure. The second effect concerns the rearrangement of the atomic bonds at the oxide-silicon interface and production of new interface states. These border traps or slow interface states become more important for sub-micron technologies when the silicon dioxide thickness decreases below 5-6nm. For e.g., properties of an MOS transistor which changes due to ionization radiation are:

1. Decrease of trans-conductance
2. Increase of leakage currents
3. Reduction of drain-source breakdown voltage
4. Deterioration of noise parameters
5. Reduction in surface mobility

High temperature annealing process is used to for recovery and it is characterized with high recovery rate.

3.1.3. Shielding against gamma radiation

Attenuation is dependent upon the atomic number Z of the used material and its density. Therefore, high Z dense shield materials are used to attenuate gamma radiation. Tantalum and tungsten are both high Z materials suitable for shielding against gamma radiation. However, their price is exorbitant, hence they are dedicated to special-purpose shielding. **Table 4** illustrates the atomic number and shielding thickness of materials used for gamma shielding.

Shield material	Atomic number Z	Tenth value layer [cm]	
		0.5 MeV	0.8 MeV
Lead	82	1.4	2.6
Copper	29	4.0	5.0
Iron	26	4.8	5.9
Alluminium	13	14.0	16.0
Concrete	-	15.0	18.0

Table 4 – Atomic numbers and TVL coefficients

3.1.4. Damage due to Neutron

Neutrons are relatively heavy particles; therefore they mainly affect the lattice atoms of a semiconductor device through collisions. Neutron interact with the matter in 2 different ways:

1. Colliding with other particles
2. Through a capture process

Elastic scattering predominates for high-energy neutrons and capture effect is more probable for low-energy. If the transferred energy is higher than displacement energy, the lattice atom will be removed from its original position in the lattice and the defect will be created. Extrinsic constituents present in a semiconductor, like impurities or doping atoms are conducive to form permanent cluster defects in a room temperature.

Neutrons are capable of ionizing atoms mainly in 3 ways:

1. Via a previously mentioned collisions and production of recoil products
2. Production of gamma rays through the de-excitation process of excited atomic nuclei
3. Neutron is absorbed by the target atomic nucleus

It should be noted that secondary particles created in this way have a high linear energy transfer (LET).

3.1.5. Shielding against neutrons

Neutrons are not charged, relatively heavy particles, therefore shielding is in this case not as easy for gamma. The design of neutron shielding is a complex process because the materials' absorption depends on the neutron energy. Besides, accurate design shielding requires the application of computational simulations using codes such as MCNP or SCALE. Neutron shielding involves 3 steps:

1. Slowing down fast high-energy penetrating neutrons
2. Absorbing the slowed down neutrons
3. Attenuating the accompanying gamma radiation created during the activation of the shielding materials.

Lead has an extremely low absorption of neutrons and therefore neutrons can easily penetrate this kind of shielding. The slowing-down process requires materials in which energy losses caused by collision are the highest. Thus, neutron should collide with particles which have similar mass, e.g. hydrogen nuclei (proton). Therefore hydrogen rich materials like hydrocarbons can be used to slow down neutrons. Thermal neutrons, with energy below 1 eV can be absorbed by the boron or cadmium materials, which have very high absorption cross-section for slow neutrons. Moreover, boron can be mixed with slowing down-materials in adequate proportions in order to obtain better attenuation, e.g. borated concrete. One has to be careful as the application of high rate of neutron capture material will result in its high activation [4].

Chapter 4

MECHANICAL, PHYSICAL AND OTHER CHARACTERISTICS OF CANDIDATE MATERIAL VERSUS KNOWN SHIELDING MATERIALS

4.0 Material Properties

There are a number of factors that need to be considered when choosing the right material for radiation shielding. The significant properties, which can affect and/or be affected due to the impact of radiation are explained in detail.

4.1. *Atomic Number*

Shielding, or the attenuation of gamma radiation, occurs through the interaction of the gamma radiation with matter. The degree to which gamma radiation is attenuated is dependent upon the energy of the incident gamma radiation, the atomic number and density of the elements in the shielding material, and the thickness of the shielding.

Shielding of gamma radiation primarily involves the interaction of gamma radiation with matter via three main processes: 1) photoelectric effect, 2) Compton scattering, and 3) pair production.

In the photoelectric effect, a gamma ray interacts with an atom resulting in the ejection of an electron from the atom. The electron receives all of the energy of the gamma ray, minus its atomic binding energy, and may induce secondary ionization events. The probability of the photoelectric effect is proportional to the atomic number (Z) of the absorbing element and inversely related to the energy of the gamma ray. Therefore, the photoelectric effect is most important for low energy gamma rays interacting with heavy elements such as lead and tungsten.

Compton scattering is similar to the photoelectric effect, in that it involves the interaction of a gamma ray with an atomic electron, resulting in the ejection of the electron from the atom. However, in Compton scattering, only a portion of the energy of gamma ray is transferred to the electron. As with the photoelectric effect, the probability of Compton scattering is proportional to the atomic number of the absorbing element (Z) and inversely proportional to the energy of the gamma ray. Compton scattering is most likely to occur for gamma rays in the 600-4000 keV range.

Pair production is less common than the photoelectric effect or Compton scattering and occurs only for very high energy gamma rays (>1022 keV). In pair production, a gamma ray is transformed into matter near the nucleus of an absorber atom in the form of an electron-positron pair. Incident gamma energy in excess of 1022 keV is transferred to the electron-positron pair as kinetic energy. The positron will eventually undergo annihilation, producing two 511 keV gamma rays, and the electron may also induce additional ionization reactions. The likelihood of pair

production, for gamma rays greater than 1022 keV, is proportional to the square of the atomic number of the absorbing atom and the logarithm of the incident gamma energy.

Shielding of 200-1500 keV gamma radiation with materials containing high Z components, such as lead and tungsten, is achieved with a significant contribution from both Compton scattering and photoelectric absorption. However, shielding with materials containing low Z components, such as iron and water, is achieved primarily with Compton scattering [11].

4.2. Density

As stated before, material density is also a factor which contributes to the degree to which gamma radiation is attenuated in radiation shielding. The denser a particular material, the more atoms it has per unit of volume. The more actual atoms in the material, the higher the chances that the gamma ray photon will collide with one of them, thus expending its energy on the lead, and not on the instruments.

Higher energy photons are only weakly attenuated by any material, so thick layers of high density high Z material are required for any significant protection [12].

A dense shield material with a high atomic number is also an efficient attenuator of X-rays. These are some of the properties which make lead an excellent shielding material [13].

Higher density materials improve the probability of Compton scattering. It also plays a role in situations where the radiation is to be stopped in the shortest possible distance. For example, in a radiation pin-hole camera (used in SPECT systems), where a small opening is needed to let the radiation through while shielding the remaining radiation, Gold is chosen as the collimator material, due to its high Linear Attenuation Coefficient [14]. In these cases, efficiency of radiation shielding will be high, even if atomic number of the shielding material is low, as the high density, and corresponding high Attenuation Coefficient makes up for it.

4.3.1 Dielectric Constant

The dielectric constant of a material, or its permittivity, is a measure of the electric field inside the material compared to the electric field in a vacuum. It is commonly used in the description of dielectric materials.

The use of state-of-the-art microelectronic devices in space radiation environments faces new challenges with the adoption of low dielectric constant (low- k) materials as inter level dielectrics. The performance in state-of-the-art microelectronic devices can no longer be improved predominantly through miniaturization of the device components as in the past. To realize future progress, the semiconductor industry has been forced to undergo an historic evolution, adopting the use of new materials such as Cu interconnects, low dielectric constant (low-k) interlayer dielectrics (ILD), metal diffusion barriers, high- materials for capacitors and gate dielectrics, and so on.

Figure 14 illustrates the concept that energetic electrons (100 keV to 10 MeV) will penetrate into interior portions of a spacecraft. Having penetrated, the electrons may be stopped in dielectrics or on ungrounded conductors. If too many electrons accumulate, the resultant high electric fields inside the spacecraft may cause an ESD to a nearby victim circuit.

Figure 14 – Illustration of internal charging process

The first step in analyzing a design for the internal charging threat is to determine the charge deposition inside the spacecraft. It is important to know the amount of charge deposited in or on a given material as well as the deposition rate as these determine the distribution of the charge and hence the local electric fields. An electrical breakdown (discharge) will occur when the local electric field exceeds the dielectric strength of the material or, between dissimilar surfaces, a critical potential. The amplitude and duration of the resulting pulse are dependent on the charge deposited. These values in turn determine how much damage may be done to spacecraft circuitry.

The dielectric constant contributes to the spacecraft charging characteristics of radiation shielding. These effects are due to interactions between the in-flight plasma environment and spacecraft electronic systems. The detrimental effects are disruption or damage from electrostatic discharges (ESD's) at interior regions of the spacecraft that may be charged by space plasmas. Although dielectrics can accumulate charge and discharge to cause damage, ungrounded conductors can also accumulate charge and must also be considered an internal charging threat. In fact, ungrounded conductors can discharge with higher peak current and higher rate of change of current, and can be a greater threat [15].

4.4. Thermal Conductivity

All of the radiations cause energy (and charge) deposition within the absorbing material through the ionization process. In water and organics, most of the absorbed ionization energy breaks chemical bonds.

In metals, almost all of the absorbed energy from ionization appears as heat. It is the kinetic energy deposition that generally manifests itself as thermal heating of the material. The corresponding temperature rise can change a number of material properties.

Apart from energy deposition, thermal conductivity of the material decreases. Studies also show an increased thermal resistance upon irradiation which can be resolved into two components. One is almost independent of temperature and is proportional to the dose; and the other increases as the 2nd or 3rd inverse power of temperature and only slowly with dose. This latter type of resistance is produced by ionizing radiation alone, and saturates at a value which seems to be dependent on the initial perfection of the crystal. It is suggested that this is the result of some form of electronic scattering [16].

4.5. *Young's Modulus*

Based on a study on radiation-sensitive polymer gels [17], it was found that, in a radiation-sensitive polymer gel used for clinical dosimetry, the Young's modulus changed significantly with radiation dose.

It is observed that there is increase in Young's modulus with electron radiation flux. It can also be noted that creep and hardness also increases with electron flux. This may be attributed to the imperfections created due to electrons, which alters the basic properties of material [18].

4.6. *Yield Strength*

Changes in mechanical properties due to radiation happen for a variety of reasons, but are generally less noticeable at higher temperatures as the damage caused by radiation is constantly being annealed out. It is observed that on irradiation, there is an increase in Yield Strength. There is also a notable increase in The Ultimate Tensile Strength, but this is less than that of yield strength.

4.7. *Currently used Radiation Shielding Materials*

Different types of ionizing radiation interact in different ways with shielding material. The effectiveness of shielding is dependent on the Stopping power of radiation particles, which varies with the type and energy of radiation and the shielding material used. Different shielding techniques are therefore used dependent on the application and the type and energy of the radiation.

The usual method for radiation protection is material shielding by spacecraft and equipment structures (usually aluminum), possibly augmented by polyethylene in human spaceflight where the main concern is high energy protons and cosmic ray ions. On unmanned spacecraft in high

electron dose environments such as Jupiter missions, or medium Earth orbit (MEO), additional shielding with materials of a high atomic number can be effective. On long duration manned missions, advantage can be taken of the good shielding characteristics of liquid hydrogen fuel and water.

4.7.1. Aluminum

Aluminum is extensively used in space applications. As such, an initial layer of shielding is provided by the satellite surface, which is composed of Aluminum. There are three types of radiation: alpha particles, beta particles and gamma rays. Beta particles can be blocked by a sheet of aluminum, but gamma rays require several inches of lead, concrete or steel to be stopped.

One of the best known properties of aluminum is that it is light, with a density one third that of steel, 2,700 kg/m³. The low density of aluminium accounts for it being lightweight but this does not affect its strength. Aluminum alloys commonly have tensile strengths of between 70 and 700 MPa. The range for alloys used in extrusion is 150 – 300 MPa. Unlike most steel grades, aluminum does not become brittle at low temperatures. Instead, its strength increases. At high temperatures, aluminum's strength decreases. At temperatures continuously above 100°C, strength is affected to the extent that the weakening must be taken into account [19].

The origin of the aluminum equivalent shield approximation in space radiation analysis can be traced back to its roots in the early years of the NASA space programs (Mercury, Gemini and Apollo) wherein the primary radiobiological concern was the intense sources of ionizing radiation causing short term effects which was thought to jeopardize the safety of the crew and hence the mission.

Aluminum is an excellent conductor of heat and electricity. An aluminum conductor weighs approximately half as much as a copper conductor having the same conductivity. Tight aluminum boxes can effectively exclude or screen off electromagnetic radiation. In this case, the better the conductivity of a material, the better the shielding qualities [20].

4.7.2. Lead

Lead shielding refers to the use of lead as a form of radiation protection to shield people or objects from radiation so as to reduce the effective dose. Lead can effectively attenuate certain kinds of radiation because of its high density and high atomic number; principally, it is effective at stopping gamma rays, and x-rays.

Lead's high density is caused by the combination of its high atomic mass and the relatively small size of its bond lengths and atomic radius. The high atomic mass means that more electrons are needed to maintain a neutral charge and the small bond length and a small atomic radius means that many atoms can be packed into a particular lead structure. Because of lead's density and large number of electrons, it is well suited to scattering x-rays and gamma-rays. These rays form photons, a type of boson, which impart energy onto electrons when they come into contact.

Without a lead shield, the electrons within a person's body would be affected, which could damage their DNA and cause cancer. When the radiation attempts to pass through lead, its electrons absorb and scatter the energy. Eventually though, the lead will degrade from the energy to which it is exposed. However, lead is not effective against all types of radiation. High energy electrons (including beta radiation) incident on lead may create bremsstrahlung radiation, which is potentially more dangerous to tissue than the original radiation. Furthermore, lead is not a particularly effective absorber of neutron radiation.

4.7.3. Tantalum

Tantalum is a heavy (specific gravity of 16.6) blue-grey metallic element with a melting point of 2,996°C. It has excellent corrosion resistance, good ductility and is resistant to most acids. It displays a number of desirable physical properties - in electronics, it forms the basis of high-performance capacitors used in electrical goods, and when alloyed with iron, imparts excellent corrosion resistance.

Similar to lead, high density and atomic number of the elements provides good radiation shielding characteristics. As such, it can be considered a good shield. However, it is observed that, interaction of certain radiation types with high Z materials may cause the production of secondary particles, which can be more harmful than the incident rays. To avoid this, studies show that multi-layered shields consisting of high and low densities is suitable, such that the secondary particles are also absorbed to a certain degree [21].

4.7.4. Water

The most penetrating ionizing radiation (gamma rays and galactic cosmic rays) can pass through aluminum but is stopped by thick and dense material such as cement. In general, the best shields will be able to block a spectrum of radiation. Aboard the space station, the use of hydrogen-rich shielding such as polyethylene in the most frequently occupied locations, such as the sleeping quarters and the galley, has reduced the crew's exposure to space radiation. Since the Space Shuttle and the International Space Station are in low Earth orbit, where the quantity and energy of the radiation is lower and the Earth's atmosphere provides protection, these spacecraft require less shielding than a base on the surface of the Moon. On the Moon, radiation shields would need to be very thick to prevent the primary cosmic rays (high-energy protons and heavy ions) from penetrating into habitation modules where astronauts will live. Such shielding could include the metal shell of a spacecraft or habitation module, an insulating layer of lunar water, or both.

Water is another hydrogen-rich molecule that can absorb radiation. However, the oxygen content in water makes it a lot heavier than polyethylene, and therefore is much more expensive to launch. Generally, lighter shields can greatly reduce the harmful effects of incoming space radiation particles, but they cannot completely stop them [22].

4.8. Candidate Materials for Proposed Design

4.8.1. Kevlar

Kevlar (poly(p-phenylene terephthalamide) - PPTA) is an organic fiber (patented by DuPont) in aromatic polyamide family designated as aramid fibres. The important properties of this class of polymers include thermal and chemical stability and the potential for high melting points, high strength and modulus.

Recently, with the aim of developing multi-function protecting structures, the capabilities of Kevlar to protect the human crews from the powerful mix of highly energetic charged particles envisaged during long duration missions have been investigated.

Test data shows Kevlar to be a good radiation shielding material, with an effectiveness close (80-90%) to that of polyethylene. The data confirms that hydrogen-rich materials (i.e., HDPE) are effective radiation shields, but also show that Kevlar, which is rich in light atoms like carbon (~50% in number), is rather effective. Nextel (and Aluminium), on the other hand, results to be much poorer radiation shielding materials and the expected reduction on dose was roughly half (and 1/3) of that provided by the same mass of polyethylene.

Apart from the radiation shielding properties, Kevlar's exceptional ballistic capabilities make it a key material for the shielding systems – existing and under development – devised to protect spacecraft from the threat posed by space debris [24].

Kevlar

- a. Chemical Formula: $C_{14}H_{14}N_2O_4$
- b. Density: 1.44 g/cc

4.8.2. Nextel

3M™ Nextel™ Aerospace Fabrics 312 are woven from strong, continuous alumina-boria-silica fibers, and are specifically designed to pass the FAA's 2000°F (1093°C) 15-minute flame penetration test. They retain strength and flexibility, with little shrinkage at continuous temperatures up to 2012°F (1100°C).

For years NASA has used 3M™ Nextel™ Ceramic Textiles to meet the demanding temperature and strength requirements of space exploration. Recently, NASA and The Johnson Space Center have used 3M™ Nextel™ Woven Ceramic Textiles to protect the command module of the Space Station Freedom-the international space station-from being punctured by space debris.

Studies which tested and compared the shielding effectiveness of Kevlar and Nextel (since they are both largely used in the construction of spacecraft) demonstrated that Kevlar is an excellent shield for heavy ions, close to polyethylene, whereas Nextel shows poor shielding characteristics. However, both Kevlar and Nextel are more effective than aluminum in the attenuation of heavy-ion dose.

Nextel 312

- a. Chemical Formula:
 - i. 62.5% Al₂O₃
 - ii. 24.5% SiO₂
 - iii. 13% B₂O₃
- b. Density: 2.7 g/cc
- c. Stoichiometry:
 - i. Al – 5
 - ii. O – 11
 - iii. Si – 1
 - iv. Bi – 1

4.8.3. Tyvek

Tyvek is a brand of flash-spun high-density polyethylene fibers, a synthetic material; the name is a registered trademark of DuPont. It is often seen used as house wrap, a synthetic material used to protect buildings during construction. The material is very strong; it is difficult to tear but can easily be cut with scissors or a knife. Water vapor can pass through Tyvek, but liquid water cannot. All of these properties make Tyvek useful in a variety of applications, including radiation shielding.

Tyvek coveralls are one-piece garments, usually white, commonly worn by mechanics, oil industry workers, painters, insulation installers, and laboratory and cleanroom workers where a disposable, one-time use coverall is needed. They are also used for some light HAZMAT applications, such as asbestos and radiation work but do not provide the protection of a full hazmat suit.

Tyvek

- a. Chemical Formula: CH₂=CH₂
- b. Density: 0.97 g/cc

4.8.4. Boron Nitride

Nanocomposites containing the light elements Boron, Nitrogen, Carbon and Hydrogen as well dispersed boron nano-particles, boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) and boron nitride nano-platelets, in a matrix, provide effective radiation shielding materials in various functional forms. Boron and nitrogen have large neutron absorption cross-sections and wide absorption spectra. The incorporation of boron and nitrogen containing nanomaterials into hydrogen containing matrices provides composites that can effectively shield against neutrons and a wide range of radiation species of all energies without fragmentation and the generation of harmful secondary particles [14].

The NASA Langley Research Center (LaRC), Jefferson National Lab (JNL), and National Institute of Aerospace (NIA) as joint owners have recently synthesized long, highly crystalline boron nitride

nanotubes (BNNT) using a novel pressure/vapor condensation method. The BNNT have extraordinary strength and high temperature stability. The BNNT are made up entirely of low Z (atomic number) atoms - boron and nitrogen. The BNNT can theoretically be processed into structural BNNT and used for load bearing structure. The BNNT are nanotubes; their molecular structure is attractive for hydrogenation [25].

Boron Nitride

- a. Chemical Formula: BN
- b. Density: 3.49 g/cc

4.8.5. Poron Foam

PORON is a fine pitch open cell urethane foam produced by Rogers Corporation. The uniform, microcellular structure allows PORON to be easily compressed for dust seals and cushions. Water sealing with PORON is possible in applications with proper compression and moderate water exposure. The average cell size of PORON foam is approximately 100 microns.

Rogers' PORON cellular urethane foam was engineered to have excellent memory (compression set resistance). The compression set resistance of PORON makes it a top pick for sealing and cushioning electronics. PORON urethane foam is manufactured by continuously casting and curing mechanically mixed formulas to the desired thickness.

Poron 4701-30 foam

- a. Chemical Formula: $C_3H_7NO_2$
- b. Density: 0.4 g/cc

4.8.6. Polyethylene

Researchers have been looking for other materials, which have higher hydrogen content than aluminum, to use as radiation shielding materials. Polymers have been a natural area of interest, due to the possibility of creating very good multi-functional materials. Polyethylene is often used along with aluminum as a benchmark for making comparisons about the radiation shielding effectiveness of a new material. Polyethylene is of particular interest because it inherently has the highest hydrogen content possible in a polymer. Furthermore, polyethylene does not contain any large nuclei, which is important because the absence of large nuclei dramatically reduces the risk of the shielding material fragmenting from a collision with a radiation ion. That is beneficial, because it reduces the number of particles that must be dealt with by an effective radiation shield [11]. **Table 5** shows the properties of known and candidate materials in context of radiation shielding characteristics.

Polyethylene (Tyvek is made from polyethylene)

- a. Chemical Formula: $CH_2=CH_2$
- b. Density: 0.95 g/cc

Material	Atomic Number	Density(g/cm ³)	Dielectric Constant (unitless)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m.k)	Youngs Modulus (GPa)	Yield Strength(MPa)
Currently used Radiation Shields						
Aluminum	13	2.7	1.7	237	68.9	276
Lead	82	11.3	25.9 (Lead Oxide)	35	14	18
Tantalum	73	16.6	11.6 (Tantalum Oxide)	57.5	186	170
Water	1(H), 8(O)	1	88	0.6065	-	-
Candidate Material						
Kevlar	6(C), 8(O), 1(H), 7(N)	1.44	4	0.04	70.5	1240
Nextel 312	13(Al), 8(O), 14 (Si), 5 (B)	2.7	5.2	0.2	138	-
Tyvek	6(C), 1(H)	0.95	2.3	0.46	52.77	-
Boron Nitride	5(B), 7(N)	2.28-3.49	7.1	7.4	100-400	83.3
Borosilicate Glass Fibres	14 (Si), 8(O), 5(B), 11(Na), 13(Al)	2.58	4.3	0.05	62.75	3445
Poron	7(N), 1(H), 6(C), 8(O)	0.4	6.3	0.06	-	1.77
Polyethylene	6(C), 1(H)	0.95	2.3	0.5	0.7	25

Table 5 – Material properties of known and Candidate materials

4.9. Summary

The radiation characteristics have been simulated using SPENVIS for Trapped Electrons, Trapped Protons, Galactic Cosmic Rays, Long Term Solar Particles and Short Term Solar Particles. This data could be used as the radiation source for designing materials for radiation shielding and simulating their effectiveness. Different codes included within SPENVIS like the GEANT4 (MULASSIS), GRAS, SHIELDOSE etc. can be used in order to record absorbed dosage and TID, using the radiation characteristics data provided within this report.

In accordance with the radiation flux values obtained from simulation, we plan to characterize different shielding materials to simulate the environment in MEO orbits. Effects of Trapped Electron flux will be used up to 6.5MeV. Similarly, Trapped Proton Flux will be used up to 10MeV. For GCR spectra of H ion, we observe a maximum differential flux of 3000 (m⁻²sr⁻¹s⁻¹) at energy level of 1000MeV, which is comparatively small. For maximum accuracy of the model, the GCR environment can be simulated with a flux of up to 10,0000 MeV.

Long Term and Short Term Solar Particle models show the recommended flux values up to a maximum energy of 500MeV. Therefore, to incorporate the solar particle radiation on the shielding material, we plan to characterize candidate material for up to 500 MeV. Further analysis and testing will be conducted to record the change in material properties due to radiation impact.

The above-mentioned materials were first simulated for TID for Trapped electrons, Trapped Protons as well as Galactic Cosmic Rays in the GPs orbit. The resulting TID, as well as Aluminum normalized TID values are shown for the candidate materials:

Chapter 5

SPENVIS SIMULATION

5.0 SPENVIS

SPENVIS is ESA's S**P**ace **E**NVironment Information System, a WWW interface to models of the space environment and its effects; including cosmic rays, natural radiation belts, solar energetic particles, plasmas, gases, and "micro-particles", using an integrated set of models of the space environment [a]. The models implemented in SPENVIS have been organized into a number of model packages, which are given below:

- Coordinate generators
- Radiation sources and effects
- Spacecraft charging
- Atmosphere and ionosphere
- Magnetic field
- Meteoroids and debris
- Data base queries
- Miscellaneous
- Geant4 tools
- ECSS space environment standard
- Planetary environment

We make use of the **Co-ordinate Generators** to define the space orbit followed by the material/entity to be simulated. For our study, specific orbit information has been taken from USA 128 GPS satellite mission and used for simulation. This orbit information is used as input for GEANT4 simulation.

We primarily use the **MULASSIS** tool within the **GEANT4 toolkit** for our simulation. The Multi-Layered Shielding Simulation (MULASSIS) tool allows the definition of a multi-layered, one-dimensional shield and incident particle source, and using the Geant4 toolkit simulates radiation transport through the geometry, treating electromagnetic and nuclear interactions.

The **SHIELDOSE tool** is briefly used to validate TID after shielding obtained from MULASSIS for Aluminum in the particular orbit simulated.

The objective of the simulation is to first, validate data obtained from an ESA publication to verify correct use of the software. This is followed by simulation using candidate materials and their combinations to find a composite which has maximum radiation shielding properties.

Ref: [a] <https://www.spennis.oma.be/intro.php>

5.1 Validation

Validation of TID for Aluminum/Tantalum multilayered composite from “Investigation on the effects of combinations of shielding materials on the total ionizing dose for the LAPLACE mission” and Simulation of Candidate materials using SPENVIS

Target Values from Graph:

Figure 1 - Dose after shielding in the Earth MEO environment for a series of total shielding masses, as a function of the aluminum mass fraction [1]

Areal thickness	Target Al Fraction = 0	Target Al Fraction = 1	Target Al Fraction = 0.2	Target Al Fraction = 0.4	Target Al Fraction = 0.6	Target Al Fraction = 0.8
0.81	3.00E+03	1.20E+04	3.00E+03	4.00E+03	6.00E+03	8.00E+03
0.95	1.30E+03	7.30E+03	1.60E+03	2.00E+03	3.00E+03	4.00E+03
1.08	8.00E+02	4.00E+03	8.00E+02	1.00E+03	1.50E+03	2.00E+03
1.22	4.70E+02	2.00E+03	5.00E+02	4.50E+02	7.00E+02	1.00E+03
1.35	3.00E+02	1.10E+03	2.20E+02	2.50E+02	4.00E+02	6.00E+02
2.16	5.00E+01	4.30E+01	3.00E+01	2.00E+01	1.10E+01	2.00E+01
2.7	4.00E+01	2.00E+01	2.00E+01	1.20E+01	1.50E+01	1.50E+01

Table 1 – Target Values from Figure 1

5.1.1 Steps taken during simulation:

MULASSIS makes the use of multiple settings for their analysis. The ESA reference publication has not mentioned majority of the settings used for simulation, and to find the correct simulation

settings, multiple MULASSIS runs were conducted with different SPENVIS settings. Given below are the common settings (Fixed settings), which were not changed for any of the runs.

The common settings for all runs were as follows:

5.1.1.1 Number of Particles – 10,000,000

The user has to give the number of incident particles to be simulated in the Monte-Carlo run. As the total time for the run is limited, this number should be chosen as small as possible but large enough to provide statistically meaningful results. As a guideline, users should first make a run with a limited number of incident particles. When the results seem to make sense, a new run with more particles can be made to improve the statistics.

The web-based SPENVIS interface has a limit of 1,000,000 particles for its simulation runs and as such, the highest possible number of particles were selected for maximum possible accuracy from the web-based system.

5.1.1.2 Energy Biasing – Don't use

Energy Biasing is used to make the simulation of the trapped particle, long-term solar particle or GCR spectra more efficient. The large range of the environmental particle spectra can make it improbable that the higher energy/low flux particles of the spectrum will be simulated. To counter this and improve the efficiency of the simulation, energy biasing can be used, which increases the probability of the low flux particles being generated. This is particularly useful when the spectrum is soft or the shielding is thick.

However, it was found that simulation results obtained from using Energy Biasing was widely deviated from values in the reference publication. It was inferred that Energy Biasing is not used for the reference paper.

5.1.1.3 Radiation Environment – Mission Based (Trapped Particles)

The 2 options for specifying the radiation environment is “Mission-Based” and “User-Defined”. Mission based radiation environment makes the use of radiation spectrum simulated using AE8 models within SPENVIS. The user defined radiation environment allows the input of specific Energy and Flux values.

Since the orbit information, and subsequent radiation spectrum is simulated using AE8 model, the “Mission-based” radiation flux is used.

5.1.1.4 Interpolation Type – Linear

As the spectra obtained from the trapped particle, long-term solar particles and GCRs models, as well as the user-defined spectrum consist of pointwise data, these can be interpolated for other energies using several interpolation methods.

Linear interpolation has been selected as the interpolation type.

5.1.1.5 Angular Distribution – Omnidirectional (Only setting possible for mission based environment)

The angular distribution can be the following options:

- a. Omnidirectional
- b. Point Source
- c. Parallel Beam
- d. None

In the case of an omnidirectional or a point source angular distribution, the minimum and maximum zenith angle to consider can be changed by the user, and the units include cm^{-2} in the case of an 1D simulation e.g. MULASSIS. If the parallel-beam option is selected and the geometry is planar slab, the user can also change the incident angle from the default normal incident case.

For a mission based environment, the omnidirectional angular distribution is recommended, and is the only possible angular distribution applicable in SPENVIS.

5.1.1.6 Analysis Parameter – Total Ionizing Dose/ particle

Four different types of analysis are available:

- Fluence
- Non-ionizing energy loss
- Energy deposition and total ionizing dose
- Pulse-height spectrum analysis

Energy deposition can be calculated for each of the layers in units of rad. As with the particle fluence, the results are normalized to the fluence normalization factor (the planar fluence of particles crossing the surface of the shield, calculated internally).

TID analysis has been done for the current simulation.

Apart from the fixed settings mentioned above, there are few variable settings and methods in SPENVIS, which has not been mentioned in the reference paper. Given below are the different analysis runs taken, their results and corresponding change made for the subsequent runs. Changes between runs have been made mostly to the method of specifying layers of Al and Ta in Spenvis, and to the cut-in ranges.

Run 1:

For Run 1, the single Aluminum layer (Al Fraction 1) was simulated for different areal densities used in the reference paper, using the fixed settings mentioned above, and default SPENVIS settings for all other variable settings.

SN	Areal Density (g/cm ²)	TID after shielding (rad)
1	0.81	1.06E+04
2	0.95	5.90E+03
3	1.08	3.26E+03
4	1.22	1.90E+03
5	1.35	1.03E+03
6	2.16	8.37E+01
7	2.7	6.13E+01

It can be noted that value of TID for Al Fraction = 1 is considerably close to the Target values given in **Table 1**. Further runs can be done to try and bring simulation results closer to the Target values. However, the TID for areal density = 2.7 g/cm² is considerably higher than the Target value (6.13E+01 and 2.00E+01 rads correspondingly). Thus subsequent runs can be concentrated on decreasing this value and bringing it closer to the Target value.

Run 2

In Run 2, Aluminum Thickness units were changed from **g/cm²** to **mm** (Areal Density to Thickness). The corresponding simulated TID after shielding for areal density 2.7 g/cm² changed from 6.13E01 to 6.8E01. That is, it increased further from the required range. Therefore, this is not an ideal change in settings.

Run 3

In Run 3, the thickness representation was changed back to areal density and a 100 um Aluminum layer was added in between last Layer and Silicon detector.

At Al Fraction 1 for 2.7 g/cm², Areal Density, the TID value increased from 6.13E+01 to 1E+02 value (Further away from expected value than previous run). This is also not a favorable outcome.

Run 4

The extra Al Layer was removed and the extrapolation type was changed from default settings to exponential.

Resulting TID value was simulated to be 0. This is not a favorable outcome.

Run 5

Extrapolation type was changed to cubic spline and simulated.

Resulting TID value was simulated to be 0. This is not a favorable outcome.

Run 6

Extrapolation type was changed back to default setting (Linear Extrapolation) and electron energy source was changed to manual tabulated form, and the flux values are entered manually, with omnidirectional linear electron input.

Resulting simulation has extremely small-simulated values of TID (E-06 range). This is not a favorable outcome.

Run 7

Electron source was changed back to “Mission based” and the cut-in range was deselected (no cut-ins).

Areal thickness	Al Fraction = 0	Al Fraction = 1
2.7	1.06E+02	2.87E+01

The TID values for Al Fraction = 1 was found to be close to the Target value, but value of Al Fraction=0 TID is not close to the corresponding target value. Further changes in settings was found to be required.

Run 8

Electron source is kept same as the previous run (Mission-Based), and the cut-in range was selected for separate regions, which includes the 2 layers. Resulting simulation results were found to not have changed from previous run.

Run 9

An Extra Aluminum Layer of 100um was added and simulated with similar conditions. Simulation resulted in error. An error on the part of the used is suspected for the simulation outcome.

Run 10

Extra Aluminum Layer was kept the same as Run 9 and the Cut-in range was changed from local region-based cut-in ranges to global cut-in range of 10um for gamma and electron production. The 100um Aluminum layer was included for all models except Al=1 and Al=0.

Calculation of Al and Ta areal density does not include the extra Aluminum layer (e.g. 0.81 g/cc areal density does not include the 100um Aluminum Layer).

5.1.2 Simulation Observations of Run 10

This simulation run showed positive results for a majority of the data points. Therefore the simulation was done for the entire set of points.

Areal thickness	Al Fraction = 0	Al Fraction = 1	Al Fraction = 0.2	Al Fraction = 0.4	Al Fraction = 0.6	Al Fraction = 0.8
0.81	2.60E+03	1.07E+04	2.82E+03	3.59E+03	4.78E+03	7.23E+03
0.95	1.22E+03	5.89E+03	1.39E+03	1.40E+03	2.22E+03	3.30E+03
1.08	9.05E+02	3.28E+03	9.94E+02	7.77E+02	1.28E+03	1.65E+03
1.22	4.83E+02	1.90E+03	4.48E+02	3.39E+02	8.89E+02	1.05E+03
1.35	5.25E+02	1.03E+03	1.58E+02	1.96E+02	4.42E+02	7.45E+02
2.16	2.76E+02	8.32E+01	7.72E+01	7.43E+01	1.44E+02	1.84E+02
2.7	1.06E+02	2.84E+01	5.36E+01	6.00E+01	6.41E+01	1.10E+02

Table 2 – Simulated values from Run 10

A comparison of simulated values and data obtained from the reference graph are plotted below for each of the Areal Densities. The blue curve in the logarithmic plot is a trend line, which represents the simulated data. The red curve shows the values obtained from the reference paper.

Figure 2 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 0.81

Figure 3 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 0.95

Figure 4 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 1.08

Figure 5 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 1.22

Figure 6 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 1.35

Figure 7 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 2.16

Figure 8 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 2.7

5.1.3. Error Analysis

The Error % for each of the values are calculated and plotted below.

Error %							
0.81	0.95	1.08	1.22	1.35	2.16	2.7	
13	6	-13	-3	-75	-452	-166	
6	13	-24	10	28	-157	-168	
10	30	22	25	22	-272	-400	
20	26	14	-27	-11	-1212	-327	
10	18	18	-5	-24	-820	-634	
11	19	18	5	7	-94	-42	

Table 3 – Error % for Run 10

From Table 3, it can be inferred that as the areal density (or material thickness) increases, the error in calculation increases, and when the areal density changes from 1.35 g/cm² to 2.16 g/cm², the error increases exponentially, to extremely high values. We can conclude that for lower areal density simulations, this model is effective in validating the ESA reference paper, but fails in higher Areal density (thickness) simulations. Thus, the model has been validated up to the Areal Density = 1.35 for this run. The large errors can be attributed to the particles used in simulation. As the material thickness increases, more number of particles are needed to maintain the accuracy of simulation. Therefore, for higher thickness simulations, we need more than 1,000,000 particles for an accurate simulation. However, the online version of SPENVIS limits the number of particles to 1,000,000 and a separate stand-alone version is required to go beyond that number. The stand-alone SPENVIS version requires authorization from ESA administration,

which was not obtained during the course of the project, due to which further investigations into the effect of TID on number of number of incident particles could not be conducted.

Figure 9 – Error % vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 0.81

Figure 10 – Error % vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 0.95

Figure 11 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 1.08

Figure 12 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 1.22

Figure 12 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 1.35

Figure 13 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 2.16

Figure 14 – Error % vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 2.7

It can be observed that the values closely match with the target values for Areal Densities 0.81 to 1.35. For the last 2 areal densities, the deviations of simulated flux values from target values are wider.

Run 11

As part of additional investigation, another run (Run 11) was conducted to obtain favorable results for Areal thickness = 2.16 g/cm² and 2.7 g/cm².

For this run, the calculation of Al and Ta areal density included the extra Aluminum layer (e.g. 0.81 g/cm² areal density includes the 100um Aluminum Layer in Overall percentage). All other settings were kept same as previous run.

5.1.4 Simulation Observations for Run 11

Areal thickness	Al Fraction = 0	Al Fraction = 1	Al Fraction = 0.2	Al Fraction = 0.4	Al Fraction = 0.6	Al Fraction = 0.8
0.81	1.86E+03	1.07E+04	2.61E+03	3.50E+03	4.51E+03	5.80E+03
0.95	9.18E+02	5.92E+03	1.05E+03	1.59E+03	2.15E+03	3.22E+03
1.08	7.99E+02	3.26E+03	7.20E+02	9.98E+02	1.18E+03	1.44E+03
1.22	3.26E+02	1.90E+03	5.20E+02	2.67E+02	4.27E+02	8.11E+02
1.35	2.53E+02	1.05E+03	2.23E+02	1.01E+02	2.33E+02	4.49E+02
2.16	1.96E+02	8.37E+01	1.45E+01	6.34E+01	1.72E+01	4.09E+01
2.7	5.78E+01	6.16E+01	1.57E+01	1.15E+01	5.35E+01	2.28E+01

Table 4 – Simulated values from Run 11

Figure 15 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 0.81

Figure 16 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 0.95

Figure 17 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 1.08

Figure 18 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 1.22

Figure 19 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 1.35

Figure 20 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 2.16

Figure 21 – Log plot of flux vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 2.7

5.1.5 Observations on Error Analysis of Run 11

The Error % for each of the values are calculated and plotted below.

Error %	0.81	0.95	1.08	1.22	1.35	2.16	2.7
	38	29	0	31	16	-292	-45
	13	34	10	-4	-1	52	21
	13	21	0	41	60	-217	4
	25	28	21	39	42	-56	-256
	28	20	28	19	25	-104	-52
	11	19	19	5	4	-95	-208

Table 5 – Error% values for Run 11

It can be observed that errors in the 2.16 g/cm² and 2.7 g/cm² areal thickness cases have significantly reduced, and errors in the 0.81 – 1.35 g/cm² cases are within acceptable ranges. Since there is no change in settings, and the only change made in Run 11 when compared to Run 10 is the calculation of Aluminum thicknesses, we can deduce that the appropriate settings have been found for SPENVIS simulation of candidate materials (Settings used by Run 10 and Run11). This is being used for all subsequent runs in SPENVIS, for the candidate materials and their combination.

Figure 22 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 0.81

Figure 22 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 0.95

Figure 22 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 1.08

Figure 23 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 1.22

Figure 24 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 1.35

Figure 25 – Error % vs AI Fraction for Areal Density = 2.16

Figure 26 – Error % vs Al Fraction for Areal Density = 2.16

It can be noted that the flux values for Areal Thickness 0.81 – 1.35 gm/cm² are close to the target values. TID values for Areal Densities 2.16 and 2.7 are farther away from Target values, but have largely reduced error % from the previous run.

5.2 Candidate Materials

Since the error between simulated and target values are least in **Run 10**, we used the corresponding SPENVIS settings and assumptions for further simulation of candidate materials. They are as follows:

1. 100 um Aluminum layer is not accounted in simulation
2. Number of particles simulated is kept constant at 10M particles
3. Particle source is Mission based – trapped electrons
4. Energy biasing is not used
5. Global Cut-in range is used for secondary electron and Bremsstrahlung emissions.

The candidate materials to be used in the composite to be developed and their properties are as follows:

2. Kevlar

- a. Chemical Formula: C₁₄H₁₄N₂O₄
- b. Density: 1.44 g/cc

3. Nextel 312

- a. Chemical Formula:
 - i. 62.5% Al₂O₃
 - ii. 24.5% SiO₂
 - iii. 13% B₂O₃

- b. Density: 2.7 g/cc
- c. Stoichiometry:
 - i. Al – 5
 - ii. O – 11
 - iii. Si – 1
 - iv. Bi – 1
- 4. Tyvek**
 - a. Chemical Formula: $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}_2$
 - b. Density: 0.97 g/cc
- 5. Boron Nitride**
 - a. Chemical Formula: BN
 - b. Density: 3.49 g/cc
- 6. Poron 4701-30 foam**
 - a. Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2$
 - b. Density: 0.4 g/cc
- 7. Polyethylene (Tyvek is made from polyethylene)**
 - a. Chemical Formula: $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}_2$
 - b. Density: 0.95 g/cc

The above-mentioned materials were first simulated for TID for Trapped electrons, Trapped Protons as well as Galactic Cosmic Rays in the GPs orbit. The resulting TID, as well as Aluminum normalized TID values are shown for the candidate materials:

5.3.0 Trapped Ionizing Dose

5.3.1 Trapped Electron Radiation

Figure 27 – TID for Trapped Electron radiation vs shielding thickness

Material	Shielding Thickness (g/cm ²)						
	0.81	0.95	1.08	1.22	1.35	2.16	2.7
Kevlar	1.35E+04	6.82E+03	3.86E+03	2.40E+03	1.54E+03	1.74E+02	1.62E+02
Nextel 312	4.47E+03	1.99E+03	1.08E+03	6.57E+02	4.80E+02	2.18E+02	1.59E+02
Tyvek	1.01E+04	5.71E+03	2.88E+03	1.84E+03	1.12E+03	4.14E+02	3.45E+02
Boron Nitride	1.82E+04	9.97E+03	5.87E+03	3.60E+03	2.08E+03	4.31E+02	2.41E+02
Poron 4701 - 30 Foam	1.10E+04	5.52E+03	3.75E+03	1.95E+03	8.71E+02	1.78E+02	2.97E+02
Aluminum	1.07E+04	5.93E+03	3.31E+03	1.85E+03	1.02E+03	9.46E+01	7.51E+01
Water	9.92E+03	5.41E+03	2.95E+03	1.68E+03	8.65E+02	2.31E+02	1.50E+02
Tantalum	2.68E+03	1.20E+03	8.88E+02	4.84E+02	5.13E+02	2.71E+02	1.02E+02

Table 6 – TID after shielding of candidate materials due to Trapped Electrons (rad)

The TID after shielding of candidate materials are compared with TID after shielding using Aluminum as a reference. We can observe that as areal density increases, the TID after shielding converges gradually towards a value close to zero. However, at higher areal densities, a further increase in areal density provides only a small decrease in TID after shielding. It can also be observed that Tantalum is the most effective in radiation shielding for Trapped Electron Radiation

5.3.2 Trapped Proton Radiation

Material	Shielding Thickness (g/cm2)						
	0.81	0.95	1.08	1.22	1.35	2.16	2.7
Kevlar	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Nextel 312	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Tyvek	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Boron Nitride	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Poron 4701-30 foam	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Aluminum	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Water	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00

Table 7 – TID after shielding of candidate materials due to Trapped protons

The TID after shielding of Trapped protons in the GPS orbit was simulated to be zero at all points.

5.3.3 Galactic Cosmic Rays

Figure 28 – TID for Galactic Cosmic Rays vs shielding thickness

Material	Shielding Thickness (g/cm ²)						
	0.81	0.95	1.08	1.22	1.35	2.16	2.7
Kevlar	8.10E-08	8.13E-08	8.15E-08	8.17E-08	8.24E-08	8.51E-08	8.70E-08
Nextel 312	8.35E-08	8.33E-08	8.38E-08	8.46E-08	8.56E-08	8.90E-08	9.01E-08
Tyvek	8.00E-08	8.09E-08	8.09E-08	8.21E-08	8.28E-08	8.39E-08	8.52E-08
Boron Nitride	8.01E-08	8.01E-08	8.16E-08	8.20E-08	8.23E-08	8.46E-08	8.50E-08
Poron 4701-30 foam	8.22E-08	8.30E-08	8.28E-08	8.31E-08	8.30E-08	8.57E-08	8.89E-08
Aluminum	8.22E-08	8.28E-08	8.35E-08	8.46E-08	8.47E-08	8.80E-08	8.85E-08
Water	8.08E-08	8.20E-08	8.18E-08	8.27E-08	8.30E-08	8.59E-08	8.68E-08
Tantalum	9.06E-08	9.05E-08	9.22E-08	9.34E-08	9.42E-08	9.74E-08	9.87E-08

Table 8 – TID after shielding of candidate materials due to Galactic Cosmic Rays

TID after shielding due to Galactic Cosmic Rays are in the smaller range (1E-8) and thus, can be neglected from the study, since the error from Trapped Electron Radiation would be greater than these values.

5.3.4 Aluminum normalized Trapped Ionizing Dose

Figure 29 – Aluminum Normalized TID for Trapped Electron Radiation vs shielding thickness

Material	Shielding Thickness (g/cm ²)						
	0.81	0.95	1.08	1.22	1.35	2.16	2.7
Kevlar	1.26	1.15	1.17	1.30	1.51	1.84	2.16
Nextel 312	0.42	0.34	0.33	0.36	0.47	2.30	2.12
Tyvek	0.94	0.96	0.87	0.99	1.10	4.38	4.59
Boron Nitride	1.70	1.68	1.77	1.95	2.04	4.56	3.21
Poron 4701 - 30 Foam	1.03	0.93	1.13	1.05	0.85	1.88	3.95
Aluminum	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Water	0.93	0.91	0.89	0.91	0.85	2.44	2.00
Tantalum	0.25	0.20	0.27	0.26	0.50	2.86	1.36

Table 9 – Aluminum normalized TID after shielding of candidate materials due to Trapped Electrons

It can be observed that the normalized TID for all points increases after 1.35 Areal Density. We can conclude that this spike in TID is due inaccurate values for higher thicknesses. As thickness increases, the number of particles needed to simulate with relatively high accuracy also correspondingly increases. Due to the limit of 10 million particles for the online SPENVIS server, we shall limit our studies to thicknesses up to 1.35 g/cm² areal densities, where the results are accurate.

5.4 Candidate Material Combinations

The following combinations of candidate materials were simulated to obtain the TID after shielding. The combinations taken were random, and thickness of each layer was maintained to be constant for the initial simulation. The total areal densities of the layers were maintained to be constant at 0.81 g/c

5.4.1 AE8/AP8 Simulation

Trial 1	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.27	5575.2
Poron	0.27	
Nextel	0.27	

Trial 2	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.162	7164.7
Poron	0.162	
Water	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Nextel	0.162	

Trial 3	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.162	5867.9
Water	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Water	0.162	
Nextel	0.162	

Trial 4	Thickness	TID
Kevlar	0.27	12423
Poron	0.27	
Kevlar	0.27	

Trial 5	Thickness	TID
Kevlar	0.162	11321
Poron	0.162	
Water	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Kevlar	0.162	

Trial 6	Thickness	TID
Kevlar	0.162	11524
Water	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Water	0.162	
Kevlar	0.162	

Trial 8	Thickness	TID
Kevlar	0.162	7099.1
Nextel	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Nextel	0.162	
Kevlar	0.162	

Trial 9	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.115714	8717.4
Water	0.115714	
BN	0.115714	
Poron	0.115714	
BN	0.115714	
Water	0.115714	
Nextel	0.115714	

Trial 10	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.81	3791.7
Al	100 um	

Trial 11	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.27	4259
BN	0.27	
Al	100 um	

Trial 12	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.81	4.24E+03

Trial 13	Thickness	TID
Kevlar	0.162	4004.1
Poron	0.162	
Nextel	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Kevlar	0.162	

Trial 15	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.27	5415.7
Tyvek	0.27	
Nextel	0.27	

Trial 14	Thickness	TID
Kevlar	0.162	3626.1
Poron	0.162	
Nextel	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Kevlar	0.162	
Al	100 um	

Trial 7	Thickness	TID
Nextel	0.162	7474.9
Kevlar	0.162	
Poron	0.162	
Kevlar	0.162	
Nextel	0.162	

5.4.2 AE8/AP8 Simulation

12 new Laminates are developed and experimented for trapped electron as shown below. Best configuration is Trail #.

Trail 1	Kevlar	0.0405	4.08E+03	Trail 5	Nextel	0.0405	3.15E+03
	Tyvek	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.648			Nextel	0.648	
	Tyvek	0.0405			Poron	0.0405	
	Kevlar	0.0405			Nextel	0.0405	
	Al	100 um			Al	100 um	

Trail 2	Nextel	0.0405	3.59E+03	Trail 6	Nextel	0.0405	3.50E+03
	Tyvek	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.648				0.0405	
	Tyvek	0.0405			Nextel	0.648	
	Nextel	0.0405			Nextel	0.0405	
	Al	100 um			Al	100 um	

Trail 4	Nextel	0.0405	3.48E+03	Trail 8	Kevlar	0.0405	3.69E+03
	Poron	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.648			Kevlar	0.0405	
	Water	0.0405			Poron	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.0405			Nextel	0.648	
	Al	100 um			Al	100 um	

Trail 9	Nextel	0.0405	3.50E+03	Trail 13	Nextel	0.0405	
	Water	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.648			Nextel	0.648	
	BN	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.0405			Nextel	0.0405	
	Al	100 um			Al	100 um	

Trail 10	Nextel	0.648	3.37E+03	Trail 14	Nextel	0.0405	4.01E+03
	Water	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.0405			Nextel	0.648	
	Poron	0.0405			Poron	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.0405			Al	0.0405	
	Al	100 um			Al	100 um	

Trail 11	Nextel	0.0405	3.76E+03	Trail 12	Nextel	0.0405	3.22E+03
	Water	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.0405			Nextel	0.648	
	Poron	0.0405			Water	0.0405	
	Nextel	0.648			Nextel	0.0405	
	Al	100 um			Al	100 um	

5.4.3. AE9/AP9 Simulation (MEAN)

Trial 1				Trial 11				Trial 15			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.27	g/cm2	2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
TID		2.56E+03	rad	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
Trial 4				Trial 11				Trial 16			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Kevlar	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.27	g/cm2	2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Kevlar	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	4	Al	100	um	4	Tyvek	0.0405	g/cm2
TID		6.88E+03	rad	TID		2.46E+03	rad	5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
Trial 7				Trial 12				Trial 17			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Nextel	0.162	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.81	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.162	g/cm2	2	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	2	Tyvek	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.162	g/cm2	TID		2.13E+03	rad	3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.162	g/cm2	Trial 13				4	Tyvek	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.162	g/cm2	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	5	Nextel	0.0405	g/cm2
6	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	6	Al	100	um
TID		3.55E+03	rad	2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
Trial 8				3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2	TID		2.16E+03	rad
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	Trial 19			
1	Kevlar	0.162	g/cm2	5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
2	Nextel	0.162	g/cm2	6	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	1	Nextel	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.162	g/cm2	TID		2.74E+03	rad	2	Water	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Nextel	0.162	g/cm2	Trial 14				3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
5	Kevlar	0.162	g/cm2	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
6	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	5	Nextel	0.0405	g/cm2
TID		4.01E+03	rad	2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	6	Al	100	um
Trial 10				3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2	7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	TID		1.93E+03	rad
1	Nextel	0.81	g/cm2	5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	Pure Aluminum			
2	Al	100	g/cm2	6	Al	100	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
3	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	1	Aluminum	0.81	g/cm2
TID		1.95E+03	rad	TID		1.83E+03	rad	2	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
Trial 11				Trial 12				Trial 13			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.27	g/cm2	2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
TID		2.56E+03	rad	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
Trial 14				Trial 15				Trial 16			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	Tyvek	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	5	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
6	Al	100	um	TID		2.74E+03	rad	6	Al	100	um
7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	Trial 17				7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
TID		1.83E+03	rad	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	TID		2.09E+03	rad
Trial 18				Trial 18				Trial 19			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Nextel	0.81	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.81	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Al	100	g/cm2	2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	2	Water	0.0405	g/cm2
3	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
TID		1.95E+03	rad	4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2	4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
Trial 19				5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2	5	Nextel	0.0405	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	6	Al	100	um	6	Al	100	um
1	Aluminum	0.81	g/cm2	7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	7	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	TID		1.83E+03	rad	TID		1.93E+03	rad
TID		5.35E+03	rad	Trial 20				Trial 21			
Trial 20				Trial 20				Trial 22			
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
1	Aluminum	0.81	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
2	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
TID		1.42E+03	rad	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 21				4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
1	Aluminum	0.81	g/cm2	Trial 22				Trial 23			
2	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		1.42E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 22				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 23				Trial 24			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 23				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 24				Trial 25			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 24				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 25				Trial 26			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 25				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 26				Trial 27			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 26				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 27				Trial 28			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 27				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 28				Trial 29			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 28				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	4	Al	100	um	4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um
2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	TID		2.46E+03	rad	TID		2.87E+03	rad
3	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	Trial 29				Trial 30			
4	detector (S)	1.00E+01	um	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit
TID		2.56E+03	rad	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2	1	Nextel	0.27	g/cm2
Trial 29				2	BN	0.27	g/cm2	2	Tyvek	0.27	g/cm2
SN	Layers	Thickness	Unit	3	Nextel						

5.5 Discussion

It can be observed from the above simulation data, that the lowest amount of TID after shielding is seen in the material sequence of Trial 14, with a TID of $3.63E+3$ after shielding, for an Areal Density of 0.81 g/cm^2 . This is very less compared to the pure aluminum TID, which is $1.07E+4$. Further variation can be done on the thickness of each layer within the composite as well as introduction of other candidate materials, and simulation with varying total Areal densities to observe how the TID after shielding can be reduced and brought as close to, or below the Tantalum shielding value of $2.68E+03$.

4.0 References

- [1] Investigation on the effects of combinations of shielding materials on the total ionising dose for the LAPLACE mission - Giovanni Santin, Marie Ansart, TEC-EES/2010.613/GS/2.0, European Space Agency.

1. Screenshot of layers used for Trial 14

Geometry: User defined ▼			
Shape: planar slab ▼		Number of layers: 7 ▼	
Layer number	Material	Thickness (unit)	Visualisation colour
Layer 1	Kevlar ▼	0.0405 g/cm2 ▼	white ▼
Layer 2	Poron_Foam ▼	0.0405 g/cm2 ▼	white ▼
Layer 3	Nextel_312 ▼	0.648 g/cm2 ▼	white ▼
Layer 4	Poron_Foam ▼	0.0405 g/cm2 ▼	white ▼
Layer 5	Kevlar ▼	0.0405 g/cm2 ▼	white ▼
Layer 6	G4_Al ▼	100 µm ▼	white ▼
Layer 7	G4_Si ▼	10 µm ▼	white ▼

Material stacking in tabular visualization in SPENVIS

There is a correction from interim report. The layers used are not uniform as depicted in Table 14 of interim report. The basis of above given dimensions is the use of 80% Nextel, and 20% Other materials in same proportion, as radiation shielding by Nextel has been simulated to more effective than other candidate materials.

2. AE9 Mean Simulation of Aluminum Fractions = 1 and 0

AE9 Mean Trapped Electron Model - Flux vs Energy Plot

Simulation generated values:

Energy	Differential Flux	Integral Flux
4.0000E-02,	1.7258E+08,	2.3179E+09
1.0000E-01,	6.5727E+07,	1.2438E+09
2.0000E-01,	3.0861E+07,	2.3661E+08
3.0000E-01,	1.8405E+07,	9.5595E+07
4.0000E-01,	1.1742E+07,	5.1505E+07

5.0000E-01,	8.1036E+06,	2.7649E+07
6.0000E-01,	6.2121E+06,	1.6569E+07
7.0000E-01,	4.7897E+06,	1.2050E+07
8.0000E-01,	3.8022E+06,	8.7858E+06
1.0000E+00,	2.4808E+06,	5.4216E+06
1.2500E+00,	1.4958E+06,	3.2243E+06
1.5000E+00,	8.6868E+05,	1.9960E+06
1.7500E+00,	4.9780E+05,	1.1745E+06
2.0000E+00,	2.8143E+05,	6.6320E+05
2.2500E+00,	1.6620E+05,	3.6542E+05
2.5000E+00,	9.8725E+04,	2.0834E+05
2.7500E+00,	6.2029E+04,	1.1917E+05
3.0000E+00,	3.9141E+04,	7.3040E+04
3.2500E+00,	2.5509E+04,	4.5117E+04
3.5000E+00,	1.6582E+04,	2.9093E+04
3.7500E+00,	1.0963E+04,	1.8662E+04
4.0000E+00,	7.2514E+03,	1.2161E+04
4.2500E+00,	4.8824E+03,	7.9246E+03
4.5000E+00,	3.2891E+03,	5.2435E+03
4.7500E+00,	2.2606E+03,	3.4069E+03
5.0000E+00,	1.5857E+03,	2.2839E+03
5.5000E+00,	8.5957E+02,	1.0703E+03
6.0000E+00,	5.1543E+02,	5.3197E+02
6.5000E+00,	3.2760E+02,	2.9631E+02
7.0000E+00,	2.1912E+02,	1.3759E+02

3. Simulation of TID after shielding for composite Trial 14:

Areal Density (g/cm ²)	TID after shielding (rad)
0.81	3.89E+03
0.95	2.09E+03
1.08	9.83E+02
1.22	3.67E+02
1.35	3.11E+02
2.16	4.50E+00
2.7	2.99E+00

4. Sensitivity of Al 100 um layer:

Change in Al Layer (%)	Aluminum Layer Thickness (um)	TID after shielding (rad)
-50	50	4.27E+03
-20	80	4.61E+03
-15	85	3.89E+03
-10	90	4.18E+03
-5	95	4.24E+03
0	100	3.88E+03
5	105	4.17E+03
10	110	4.22E+03
15	115	4.26E+03
20	120	4.02E+03
50	150	3.71E+03

Questions

- (1) Trial 14 is 0.81 g/cm² with the individual layer thicknesses as shown. So what are the thicknesses of layers in the Table for Item 3 and Trial 14? The areal densities are from 0.81 to 2.7.
- (2) Item4 – Confirming that sensitivity of Al 100 um layer is also for 0.81 g/cm² and Trial 14 thicknesses. Looks like 100 um is optimized by Santin.
- (3) Did you get a chance to vary the cut in range which is 1 um at present.
- (4) Is there a way to obtain the electron and Bremsstrahlung fluxes after Layer 6 at the Si detector?
- (5) Lastly I am assuming that you are using AE9 for all simulations henceforth.

Response

1. As stated in response to the previous set of queries, the thicknesses shown for Trial 14 has to be corrected. The actual dimensions used are as follows:

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
Nextel	0.681	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

The above mentioned thicknesses are for the 0.81 g/cm² areal density case (Trial 14). Given below are the layer thickness used for each case in item 3:

a. Total Areal Density = 0.81

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
Nextel	0.648	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

b. Total Areal Density = 0.95

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.0475	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0475	g/cm ²
Nextel	0.76	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0475	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.0475	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

c. Total Areal Density = 1.08

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.054	g/cm ²
Poron	0.054	g/cm ²
Nextel	0.864	g/cm ²
Poron	0.054	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.054	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

d. Total Areal Density = 1.22

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.061	g/cm ²
Poron	0.061	g/cm ²
Nextel	0.976	g/cm ²
Poron	0.061	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.061	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

e. Total Areal Density = 1.35

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.0675	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0675	g/cm ²
Nextel	1.08	g/cm ²
Poron	0.0675	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.0675	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

f. Total Areal Density = 2.16

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.108	g/cm ²
Poron	0.108	g/cm ²
Nextel	1.728	g/cm ²
Poron	0.108	g/cm ²
Kevlar	0.108	g/cm ²
Aluminum	100	Um

Silicon	10	Um
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g. Total Areal Density = 2.7

Material	Thickness	Unit
Kevlar	0.135	g/cm2
Poron	0.135	g/cm2
Nextel	2.16	g/cm2
Poron	0.135	g/cm2
Kevlar	0.135	g/cm2
Aluminum	100	Um
Silicon	10	Um

2. Yes. The Aluminum sensitivity study was done for Trial 14, which is based on Overall Areal Density of 0.81 g/cm2.

3. For the above simulations, the cut-in ranges were constantly kept at 10um for both Electron and Gamma production. Please find below, the simulation results for varying cut-in ranges for Areal Density = 0.81 g/cm2. Please note that this simulation has been done using AE9 model, as specified.

Figure 1

This is different from the previous AE9 run, which was done for AL1 and AL0 as we are not taking the mean flux values for simulation. We are using a percentile setting for the simulation, which can be expected to generate higher TID values.

Cut-in range	TID after shielding
1	9.57E+03
3	9.86E+03
5	9.82E+03
10	9.89E+03
15	9.90E+03
20	9.90E+03

4. It is possible to obtain secondary electron and Gamma ray flux between the different layers through the following interface in MULASSIS. The simulation has been shown for a total areal density of 0.81 g/cm².

Secondary Electron Flux:

Analysis type: Fluence

Fluence analysis

Select particle type(s) for fluence analysis: incident particle
 electron
 gamma

Output units: /cm²

Fluence density type: omni-directional

Select boundaries between layers for fluence analysis:
 source 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 target

Energy binning mode: default

Angle binning mode: default

Reset Save >>

Figure 2

SPENVIS simulation results:

Figure 3

Gamma Ray flux:

Analysis type: Fluence ▼	
Fluence analysis	
Select particle type(s) for fluence analysis:	incident particle ▲ electron gamma ▼
Output units:	/cm2 ▼
Fluence density type:	omni-directional ▼
Select boundaries between layers for fluence analysis:	
source	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 7 <input type="checkbox"/> target
Energy binning mode:	default ▼
Angle binning mode:	default ▼
<input type="button" value="Reset"/> <input type="button" value="Save >>"/>	

Figure 4

SPENVIS simulation results:

Figure 5

5. Yes. we are using AE9 for all simulations henceforth.

SPENVIS Report

Sept - 25 - 2016

Tasks for the week:

1. Use both Mean and 95% AE9/AP9 and compare Tantalum, Aluminum and layered Composite (LC). LC means the best configuration of Trial 14 .
2. Carryout for MEO spectrum, repeat Figure 5 of the esa paper for all the thicknesses as given in Figure 5.
3. For Benchmarking the modeling, use SHIELDOSE-2 from within SPENVIS and compute TID for AI=1 between 0.81 – 2.7 g/cm² . Plot together with MULASSIS results for AI=1. Geometry is planar slab.
4. Check all the materials if they are approved by NASA
5. For LC, plot effectiveness of each individual layer i.e. plot the spectrums before and after a layer for each layer i.e. in the same plot, there will be multiple curves at 7 locations as given in figure below:

Simulation Results:

Different variations of Trial 14 combination of material layers were simulated as shown below. The simulation was carried out for both AE9 mean and AE9 95 percentile radiation spectrums. The different variations were done for a Total Areal Density of 0.81 g/cm².

1. Variation of Trial 14 Layers for 0.81 g/cm² areal density:

1.1. Original Trial 14:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm ²
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm ²
TID after shielding		9885.5	rad

AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
3	Nextel	0.648	g/cm ²
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm ²
5	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm ²
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um

Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		1832.9	rad

1.2. Variation a:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		9121.4	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		1871.1	rad

1.3. Variation b:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		9056.8	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2

TID after shielding		1655.4	rad
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1.4. Variation c:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
2	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		6677.3	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
2	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		2270.9	rad

1.5. Variation d:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		11432	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Nextel	0.648	g/cm2
2	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
3	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
4	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		2511	rad

1.6. Variation e:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.081	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		7309.3	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.081	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		1612.2	rad

1.7. Variation f:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		8397.6	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Kevlar	0.0405	g/cm2
2	Poron	0.0405	g/cm2
3	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
4	Kevlar	0.081	g/cm2
5	Nextel	0.324	g/cm2
6	Aluminum	100	um
Detector	Silicon	10	um
Total		0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		1892.5	rad

1.8. Tantalum:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units

1	Tantalum	0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		6099.3	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Tantalum	0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		1517.8	rad

1.9. Aluminum:

AE9 95% percentile model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Aluminum	0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		25854	rad
AE9 mean model			
Layer	Material	Thickness	Units
1	Aluminum	0.81	g/cm2
TID after shielding		5482.9	rad

Among the variations shown above, for AE9 Mean model, variation b can be considered the best option, according to the AE9 mean model, and variation c can be considered the best option, according to AE9 95 percentile model. In fact, if we follow the AE9 95 percentile model, we can observe that TID after shielding for the candidate material composition is considerably close to the value obtained for Tantalum. Therefore for all further simulation, all AE9 mean simulations use variation b of Trial 14 and AE9 95 percentile simulations use Variation c of Trial 14.

2. MEO spectrum was as shown in Figure 5 of Santi-n Report was simulated and- shown in Report titled “SPENVIS Combined Report 08-15-2016.

3. Benchmarking using Shieldose 2:

Shieldose 2 was used to benchmark the data and the corresponding plot is shown together with MULASSIS results and LC composites. LC used for AE9 mean and AE9 95 percentile models are different, as specified above.

Figure 1 - Plot with SHIELDOSE and MULASSIS TID after shielding (AE9 mean)

Figure 2 - Plot with SHIELDOSE and MULASSIS TID after shielding (AE9 95 percentile)

AE9 mean Model				
Thickness	Tantalum	Aluminum	LC	Shieldose AL
0.81	1.52E+03	5.47E+03	1.81E+03	8.00E+03
0.95	7.87E+02	3.14E+03	9.00E+02	4.20E+03
1.08	4.67E+02	2.07E+03	4.76E+02	2.44E+03

1.22	2.56E+02	1.18E+03	2.95E+02	1.44E+03
1.35	1.19E+02	4.96E+02	1.39E+02	9.31E+02
2.16	1.91E+01	1.47E+02	1.41E+01	1.86E+02
2.7	3.46E+01	3.06E+01	1.58E+01	1.29E+02

Table 1 - Values used for Figure 1 (AE9 mean)

Thickness	Shieldose AL	Aluminum	Tantalum	LC
0.81	3.37E+04	2.57E+04	6.08E+03	6.52E+03
0.95	1.78E+04	1.36E+04	4.46E+03	3.94E+03
1.08	1.04E+04	7.38E+03	1.88E+03	2.77E+03
1.22	6.10E+03	4.44E+03	9.98E+02	8.10E+02
1.35	3.92E+03	2.79E+03	7.82E+02	1.27E+03
2.16	7.13E+02	6.49E+02	8.55E+02	0
2.7	4.76E+02	5.66E+01	5.59E+02	1.07E+01

Table 2 - Values used for Figure 2 (AE9 95 percentile)

5. Spectrum after Each Layer:

For a total Areal Density of 0.81 g/cm², the candidate material combination (LC) was simulated and the incident particle spectra was generated for each layer. Each layer and the corresponding spectrum has been shown in the figures below:

5.1 Boundary between Source and Layer 1:

Figure 3 - Radiation Spectrum between Source and Layer 1(AE9 mean Model)

Figure 4 - Radiation Spectrum between Source and Layer 1(AE9 95 percentile)

5.2 Boundary between Layer 1 and Layer 2

Figure 5 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 1 and 2 (AE9 mean Model)

Figure 6 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 1 and 2 (AE9 95 percentile)

5.3 Boundary between Layer 2 and Layer 3:

Figure 7 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 2 and 3(AE9 mean Model)

Figure 8 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 2 and 3(AE9 95 percentile)

5.4 Boundary between Layer 3 and Layer 4:

Figure 9 - Radiation spectrum between Layers 3 and 4 (AE9 mean model)

**Figure 10 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 3 and 4 (AE9 95 percentile)
5.5 Boundary between Layer 4 and Layer 5:**

Figure 11 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 4 and 5(AE9 mean model)

Figure 12 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 4 and 5 (AE9 95 percentile)

5.6 Boundary between Layer 5 and Layer 6:

Figure 13 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 5 and 6 (AE9 mean model)

Figure 14 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 5 and 6 (AE9 95 percentile)

5.7 Boundary between Layer 6 and Aluminum Layer:

Figure 15 - Radiation Spectrum between Layers 6 and Aluminum Layer(AE9 mean model)

**Figure 16 - Radiation Spectrum between Layer 6 and Aluminum Layer(AE9 95 percentile)
5.8 Boundary between Aluminum Layer and Detector:**

Figure 17 - Radiation Spectrum between Aluminum Layer and Detector(AE9 mean model)

Figure 18 - Radiation Spectrum between Aluminum Layer and Detector(AE9 95 percentile)

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APPENDIX

A **Quality Function Deployment (QFD)** analysis of the various materials being considered:

Requirements	Priority	Tantalum	Aluminum	Trial # 5
Primary Radiation	10	10	2.5	9
Secondary Radiation	5	2	8	10
Density	7	2	8	10
Cost	3	2	10	8
Total Score		10x10+5x2+7x2+3x2=130	151	234

Conclusion:

This justifies superiority of Trial # 5 over Aluminum and Tantalum based on above mentioned four requirements and corresponding priority numbers. **Considering Tantalum as 1, Aluminum is 151/130 i.e. 1.16 times better and Trial #5 is 234/130 = 1.8 times better.**

Data used are:

Cost :

- Tantalum = \$150 / kg
- Aluminum = \$2.5/kg
- Poron = \$0.2/kg
- Nextel = \$125/kg

Density (sp gr):

- Tantalum = 16.6
- Aluminum = 2.8
- Poron = 0.4
- Nextel = 2.7
- Water = 1.0

Trapped Electron (from SPENVIS) (TID) for the same areal density of 0.81 gm/cc

- Tantalum = 2680
- Aluminum = 10700
- Trial # 5 (Nextel/Water/Nextel/Poron/Nextel) = 3150